

Expressing clock time in the languages of Europe. List of sources.

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1. Башевеишвили Л. О. Учебник грузинского языка. Часть 1. М.: Вост. лит., 2007. — 455 с.
2. Бернштейн С. Б. Болгарско-русский словарь. М.: Государственное издательство иностранных и национальных словарей, 1953. — 886с.
3. Болгарско-русский параллельный корпус. URL: http://rbcorpus.com/contact_rus.php# (Дата обращения: 2023–2024 гг.)
4. Гинина С. Ц., Платонова И. В., Усикова Р. П. Учебник болгарского языка. М.: Изд-во Моск. Ун-та, 1985. — 440 с.
5. Лишкова М. (отв. ред). Чешский язык. Учебник для начинающих. Прага: Svět sovětů, 1964. — 135 с.
6. Национальный корпус русского языка 2003–2019. URL: <http://www.ruscorpora.ru/> (Дата обращения: 2023–2024 гг.)
7. Чешский национальный корпус. URL: <https://www.korpus.cz/> (Дата обращения: 2023–2024 гг.).
8. Шведова. Н. Ю. Шведова. Русская грамматика. Изд-во Наука, 1980. Т. 1. — 784 с.
9. Abondolo D. Colloquial Finnish. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2012. — 354 p.
10. Alday U. O. Colloquial Spanish 2: the next step in language learning. Routledge, 2018. — 286 p.
11. Alday U. O. Colloquial Spanish: the complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2015. — 328 p.
12. Alexander R. Bosnian, Croatian, Serbian, a grammar: With sociolinguistic commentary. Univ of Wisconsin Press, 2006. — 464 p.
13. Antova E., Boichinova E., Benatova P. A short grammar of Bulgarian for English speaking learners. Sofia: AVM Commerce, 1991.
14. Avetisyan A. S. Eastern Armenian: comprehensive self-study language course. – Haghinakayin hratarakut‘yun, 2008. — 219 p.
15. Bielec D. Polish: An essential grammar. Routledge, 2012. — 432 p.

16. Birnbaum Salomo A. Yiddish: a survey and a grammar. University of Toronto Press, 2016.
17. Bråtveit K., Glyn Jones W., Gade K. Colloquial Norwegian. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 1995. — 282 p.
18. British national corpus. URL: <http://www.natcorp.ox.ac.uk/>. (Дата обращения: 2023–2024 гг.).
19. Butt J. B., Benjamin C., Antonia M. R. A new reference grammar of modern Spanish. Routledge, 2018. — 620 p.
20. Declerck, Renaat. A comprehensive descriptive grammar of English. Tokyo: Kaitakusha, 1991. — 506 p.
21. Dindelegan G. P., Maiden M. (ed.). The grammar of Romanian. Oxford University Press, 2013. — 656 p.
22. Donaldson B. Colloquial Dutch. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2016. — 346 p.
23. Duensing A., Batstone C. Colloquial German: the next step in language learning. Routledge, 2010. — 226 p.
24. Dum-Tragut J. Armenian: Modern Eastern Armenian. – John Benjamins Publishing, 2009. Т. 14. — 743 p.
25. Elordi B. O., King A. R. Colloquial Basque: A complete language course. – Routledge, 2015.
26. Gade K., Jones W. G. Colloquial Danish: The Complete Course for Beginners. Routledge, 2003. — 294 p.
27. Göksel A., Kerslake C. Turkish: A comprehensive grammar. Routledge, 2004. — 624 p.
28. Gönczöl R. Romanian: an essential grammar. Routledge, 2020. — 294 p.
29. Gonczol-Davies R., Deletant D. Colloquial Romanian. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2004. — 328 p.
30. Goodwin W. W. A Greek grammar. Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2003. — 488 p.
31. Hagopian G. Armenian for everyone: Western and Eastern Armenian in parallel lessons. Caravan Books, 2005. — 516 p.
32. Hammond L. Serbian: An essential grammar. Routledge, 2004. — 336 p.
33. Harms R. T. Estonian grammar. Routledge, 2017. — 190 p.

34. Hatherall D. *Colloquial German: The Complete Course for Beginners*. Routledge, 2003. — 353 p.
35. Hauge K. R., Tisheva Y. *Colloquial Bulgarian*. Routledge, 2015. — 296 p.
36. Hawkesworth C. *Colloquial Croatian and Serbian. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 1998. — 309 p.
37. Hawkins R., Towell R. *French grammar and usage*. Routledge, 2015. — 464 p.
38. Herrity P. *Slovene: A comprehensive grammar*. Routledge, 2015. — 508 p.
39. Hewitt G. *Georgian: A learner's grammar*. Routledge, 2005. — 482 p.
40. Holmes P., Hinchliffe I. *Swedish: A comprehensive grammar*. Routledge, 2013. — 744 p.
41. Holmes P., Hinchliffe I. *Swedish: An essential grammar*. Routledge, 2020. — 234 p.
42. Holmes Ph., Serin G. *Colloquial Swedish. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 1996. — 321 p.
43. Hualde J. I., De Urbina J. O. (ed.). *A grammar of Basque*. Mouton de Gruyter, 2003. — 943 p.
44. Hutchinson A. P., Lloyd J., Sousa C. *Portuguese: an essential grammar*. Routledge, 2018. — 284 p.
45. Vilatarsana M. T. *L'expressió de les hores en català: anàlisi contrastiva // Caplletra. Revista Internacional de Filologia. №. 30. 2001. P. 169–198.*
46. Ibarz A., Ibarz T. *Colloquial Catalan: A Complete Course for Beginners*. Routledge, 2015. — 310 p.
47. Janda L. A., Townsend C. E. *Czech*. 2000. URL: https://jakobson.korpus.cz/~rosen/public/GGG/czech_grammar.pdf/ Accessed 2023–2024.
48. Javarek V., Sudjic M. *Teach Yourself Serbo-Croat*. London: English Universities Press, 1963. — 212 p.
49. Jeroen A., Backus A. *Colloquial Turkish. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2000. — 352 p.
50. Kahn L. *Colloquial Yiddish. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2012. — 320 p.
51. Kalnača A., Lokmane I. *Latvian grammar*. University of Latvia Press, 2021. — 559 p.

52. Karlsson F. Finnish: A comprehensive grammar. Routledge, 2017. — 518 p.
53. Karlsson F. Finnish: An essential grammar. Routledge, 2013. — 280 p.
54. King G. Colloquial Welsh: A complete language course. Routledge, 2004.
55. Krishna Bhattacharya, A. K. Basu. An Intensive Course in Bengali. Central Institute of Indian Languages, 1981. — 636 p.
56. Lymbery S. Colloquial Italian: the complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2015. — 368 p.
57. Lymbery S., Silipo S. Colloquial Italian 2: the next step in language learning. Routledge, 2015. — 223 p.
58. Maiden M., Robustelli C. A reference grammar of modern Italian. Routledge, 2014. — 512 p.
59. Makharoblidze T. A short grammar of Georgian. Lincom Europa, 2009. — 120 p.
60. Martirosyan H. Etymological dictionary of the Armenian inherited lexicon // Etymological Dictionary of the Armenian Inherited Lexicon. Brill, 2009. — 951 p.B
61. Mazur B. W. Colloquial Polish. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 1983. — 319 p.
62. McGonagle N. Irish grammar: A basic handbook. Hippocrene Books, 1998. — 100 p.
63. McGrath C. G. Irish. Complete course for beginners // Living language. Random house, 2009. — 273 p.
64. McIntyre B., Sampaio J. Colloquial Portuguese. Routledge, 2012. — 313 p.
65. Mëniku L., Campos H. Colloquial Albanian. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2012. — 329 p.
66. Moseley C. Colloquial Estonian. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2008. — 257 p.
67. Naughton J., von Kunes K. Czech: An essential grammar. Routledge, 2020. — 354 p.
68. Naughton J., von Kunes K. Slovak. The complete course for beginners. Routledge, 2012. — 366 p.
69. Neijmann D. L. Colloquial Icelandic: the complete course for beginners. — Routledge, 2015. — 214 p.
70. Newmark L., Hubbard P., Prifti P. R. Standard Albanian: A reference grammar for students. Stanford University Press, 1982. — 347 p.

71. Oosterhoff J. *Modern Dutch Grammar: a practical guide*. Routledge, 2014. — 287 p.
72. Pirnat-Greenberg M. *Colloquial Slovene. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2012. — 314 p.
73. Prauliņš D., Moseley C. *Colloquial Latvian. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2010. — 266 p.
74. Press I., Le Bihan H. *Colloquial Breton: the complete course for beginners*. — Psychology Press, 2004. — 294 p.
75. Press I., Pugh S. *Colloquial Ukrainian*. Routledge, 2014. — 384 p.
76. Press I., Pugh S. *Ukrainian: A comprehensive grammar*. Routledge, 2015. — 315 p.
77. Ramonienė M. et al. *Lithuanian: A Comprehensive Grammar*. Routledge, 2019. — 354 p.
78. Ramonienė M., Press I. *Colloquial Lithuanian. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2011. — 815 p.
79. Roparz H. *Cours Elementaire de Breton*. Al Liamm, 1960.
80. Rounds C. *Hungarian: An essential grammar*. Routledge, 2009. — 320 p.
81. Rounds C. H., Sólyom E. *Colloquial Hungarian. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2002. — 317 p.
82. Sadowska I. *Polish: A comprehensive grammar*. Routledge, 2012. — 672 p.
83. Scott Britton A. *Catalan dictionary and phrasebook*. New York: Hippocrene books, 2013. — 213 p.
84. Spadaro K. M., Graham K. *Colloquial Scottish gaelic: the complete course for beginners*. — Psychology Press, 2001. — 334 p.
85. Stumbrienė V., Kaškelevičienė A. *Nė dienos be lietuvių kalbos*. Gimtasis žodis, 2004.
86. Thacker M., d'Angelo C. *Essential French Grammar*. Routledge, 2014. — 528 p.
87. The online encyclopedia of writing systems and languages. URL: <https://www.omniglot.com/> (Дата обращения: 2023–2024 гг.)
88. Timberlake A. *A reference grammar of Russian*. Cambridge University Press, 2004. — 510 p.
89. Watts N. *Colloquial Greek. The complete course for beginners*. Routledge, 2004. — 355 p.

90. White L. Aurrera!: a textbook for studying Basque. Nevada: University of Nevada Press, 1949. — 423 p.